

STUDIES OF CARBONYL COMPOUNDS. PART I. THE FORMATION
OF THE SODIUM DERIVATES OF SUBSTITUTED MALON
AND METHYLMALON AMIDES

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Carbonyl compounds such as the disubstituted amides of malonic and methylmalonic esters have been heated with molecular sodium, and it is found that monosodium derivatives are obtained.

With a view to studying the reactivity of the hydrogens of the reactive methylene ($-\text{CH}_2-$) group Naik and Shah (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 45) took up the study of sodium compounds of the substituted amides of cyanoacetic ester and prepared monosodium compounds of the general formula, $\text{CN}.\text{CHNa}.\text{COR}$, where $\text{R} = \text{OEt}$, NH_2 , NHMe , etc. Similar monosodium derivatives of the disubstituted amides of malonic and methylmalonic esters have been prepared by the author under similar experimental conditions. The main results of the work may be summarised thus :

Type I. Conversion of $\text{H}_2\text{C}(\text{CO}.\text{NH}.\text{R})_2$ into $\text{HNaC}(\text{CO}.\text{NH}.\text{R})_2$ where $\text{R} =$ phenyl, *o*-tolyl, *m*-tolyl, *p*-tolyl, α -naphthyl, β -naphthyl, 1:4:5-xylyl or benzyl group.

Type II. Conversion of $\text{HCH}_3\text{C}(\text{CONH}.\text{R})_2$ into $\text{NaCH}_3\text{C}(\text{CO}.\text{NH}.\text{R})_2$ where $\text{R} =$ *p*-tolyl or *o*-tolyl.

Malonamide, malon monophenylamide and malon-mono-*o*-tolylamide are found to remain unreacted under the experimental conditions.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Monosodio-malon-di-phenylamide, was obtained by adding malon-diphenylamide (2.5 g.) to molecular sodium (0.5 g.) in presence of about 30 c.c. of dry benzene, and heating under reflux for 6 hours, at the end of which the excess of sodium melted and stuck at the bottom of the flask. The sodium compound separated out from benzene. The white amorphous mass was filtered and washed with light petroleum. It was then dried in a desiccator over anhydrous calcium chloride and phosphorus pentoxide. It slowly turns yellow above 60° , turns red and shrinks above 203° , slowly decomposes and chars above 210° , and does not melt even at 270° . The other sodio compounds are listed in Table I.

It is practically insoluble in benzene, toluene, ether and light petroleum. (Found : N, 10.42 ; Na, 8.04. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{Na}$ requires N, 10.14 ; Na, 8.33 per cent).

TABLE I

	M. p.	Formula	Analysis.	
			Found.	Calc.
Monosodio-malon-di- <i>p</i> -tolylamide	Turns yellow and shrinks above 130°; turns reddish above 200°, decomposes and chars above 252°.	$C_{17} H_{17} O_2 N_2 Na$	Na 7.30	7.56
Monosodio-malon-di- <i>m</i> -tolylamide	Turns yellow and shrinks above 145°; turns red above 220°, decomposes and chars above 245°	$C_{17} H_{17} O_2 N_2 Na$	7.40	7.56
Monosodio-malon-di- <i>o</i> -tolylamide	Shrinks above 90°, turns yellow above 180°, m.p. 200° (decomp.)	$C_{17} H_{17} O_2 N_2 Na$	7.35	7.56
Monosodio-malon-di- α -naphthylamide	Shrinks above 155°, m.p. 173°	$C_{23} H_{17} O_2 N_2 Na$	5.79	6.12
Monosodio-malon-di- β -naphthylamide	Shrinks above 200°, m.p. 215° (decomp.)		5.77	6.12
Monosodio-malon-di-1:4:6-xylidide	Shrinks above 215°, m.p. 228° (decomp.)	$C_{16} H_{21} O_2 N_2 Na$	6.84	6.93
Monosodio-malon-di- <i>n</i> -propylamide	Shrinks above 125°, turns yellow above 180°, turns reddish yellow above 225° not melting at 270°	$C_9 H_{17} O_2 N_2 Na$	11.12	11.06
Monosodio-malon-di-benzylamide	Shrinks above 155°, decomposes and chars at a higher temp.	$C_{17} H_{17} O_2 N_2 Na$	7.20	7.66
Monosodio-methylmalon-di- <i>p</i> -tolylamide	Shrinks above 120°, turns yellow above 150°, reddish above 182°, decomposes and chars above 265°	$C_{18} H_{19} O_2 N_2 Na$	6.89	7.33
Monosodio-methylmalon-di- <i>o</i> -tolylamide	Shrinks and turns yellow above 175°, m.p. 182° (decomp.)	$C_{18} H_{19} O_2 N_2 Na$	7.14	7.23

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